

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

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2 **Supplemental Table S1.** Amounts of daily abomasally infused supplements¹ (Vogel et al., 2020)

Supplementation	Treatments						
	CTRL ²	EFA		CLA ²	EFA+CLA		
	Coconut oil ³	Linseed oil ⁴	Safflower oil ⁵	Lutalin ^{®6}	Linseed oil ⁴	Safflower oil ⁵	Lutalin ^{®6}
Daily infused oils (g/d)							
Dosage lactation	76	78	4	38	78	4	38
Dosage dry period	38	39	2	19	39	2	19
Daily infused fatty acids (g/d) at dosage lactation ⁷							
18:3 <i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15	0.00	39.9	0.01	0.00	39.9	0.01	0.00
18:2 <i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12	1.39	12.4	2.48	1.34	12.4	2.48	1.34
18:2 <i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -11	0.00	0.00	0.01	10.3	0.00	0.01	10.3
18:2 <i>trans</i> -10, <i>cis</i> -12	0.00	0.02	0.01	10.2	0.02	0.01	10.2

¹Cows were supplemented daily with coconut oil (CTRL), linseed and safflower oil (EFA), Lutalin[®] (CLA, *cis*-9, *trans*-11 and *trans*-10, *cis*-12 CLA), or EFA+CLA.

²Addition of Vitamin E (0.06 g/d), Covitol 1360 (BASF, Ludwigshafen, Germany), to compensate for Vitamin E in linseed oil (0.07%) and safflower oil (0.035%).

³Sanct Bernhard, Bad Ditzenbach, Germany

⁴DERBY, Derby Spezialfutter GmbH, Münster, Germany

⁵GEFRO, Memmingen/Allgäu, Germany

⁶BASF, Ludwigshafen, Germany

⁷The dosage lactation was halved during dry period.

4 **Supplemental Table S2.** Fatty acid composition of the daily infused supplements during lactation¹ (Vogel et al., 2020)

Fatty acid (%)	CTRL ²		EFA ³		CLA ⁴	EFA+CLA ⁵
	Coconut oil	Linseed oil	Safflower oil	Total	Lutalin [®]	Total
SFA	89.4	10.4	12.3	10.5	11.1	10.7
6:0	0.93	–	–	–	–	–
8:0	9.85	–	–	–	–	–
10:0	6.10	–	–	–	–	–
12:0	45.5	–	–	–	–	–
14:0	16.9	0.02	0.09	0.02	–	0.02
16:0	6.87	5.78	7.63	5.87	6.23	5.98
17:0	–	0.03	–	0.03	–	0.02
18:0	3.10	4.11	3.71	4.10	4.19	4.13
20:0	0.11	0.19	0.42	0.20	0.22	0.21
22:0	–	0.13	0.25	0.14	0.37	0.21
24:0	–	0.09	0.16	0.10	0.10	0.10

MUFA	8.35	21.5	23.5	21.6	29.5	24.1
16:1, <i>cis</i> -9	–	0.07	0.12	0.07	0.09	0.08
18:1, <i>cis</i> -9	8.35	20.7	22.4	20.8	28.3	23.1
18:1, <i>cis</i> -11	–	0.61	0.66	0.61	0.67	0.63
20:1, <i>cis</i> -11	–	0.16	0.23	0.16	0.51	0.27
24:1, <i>cis</i> -15	–	–	0.11	0.01	–	< 0.01
PUFA	1.83	67.1	62.5	66.9	3.75	46.9
18:2, <i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12	1.83	15.9	62.0	18.2	3.52	13.5
18:2, <i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -12	–	–	–	–	0.08	0.03
18:2, <i>trans</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12	–	–	–	–	0.07	0.02
18:3, <i>cis</i> -6, <i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12	–	–	0.05	< 0.01	0.07	0.02
18:3, <i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15	–	51.1	0.24	48.7	–	33.3
20:2, <i>cis</i> -11, <i>cis</i> -14	–	0.06	–	0.06	–	0.04
20:3, <i>cis</i> -11, <i>cis</i> -14, <i>cis</i> -17	–	0.02	–	0.02	–	0.02
22:5, <i>cis</i> -7, <i>cis</i> -10, <i>cis</i> -13, <i>cis</i> -16, <i>cis</i> -19	–	–	0.28	0.01	–	0.01
CLA	< 0.05	0.02	0.32	0.04	54.4	17.2

18:2, <i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -11 CLA	–	–	0.12	0.01	27.2	8.61
18:2, <i>trans</i> -10, <i>cis</i> -12 CLA	–	0.02	0.20	0.03	27.0	8.56
18:2, <i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -11 CLA	–	–	–	–	0.23	0.07

5 ¹Dosage of oil supplementation was halved during the dry period in all groups, respectively.

6 ²Control (CTRL, n=9): 76 g/d coconut oil (Bio-Kokosöl #665, Kräuterhaus Sanct Bernhard KG, Bad Ditzgenbach, Germany) and 0.06 g/d Vitamin E
7 (Covitol[®]1360, BASF SE, Ludwigshafen, Germany), 1.48 MJ NE_L/d

8 ³Essential fatty acids (EFA, n = 9): 78 g/d linseed (DERBY[®] Leinöl #4026921003087, DERBY Spezialfutter GmbH, Münster, Germany) and 4 g/d
9 safflower oil (GEFRO Distelöl, GEFRO Reformversand Frommlet KG, Memmingen, Germany), comprised 0.06 g/d Vitamin E, 1.57 MJ NE_L/d

10 ⁴Conjugated linoleic acid (CLA, n = 10): 38 g/d Lutalin[®] (BASF SE, Ludwigshafen, Germany) and 0.06 g/d Vitamin E (Covitol[®]1360, BASF SE,
11 Ludwigshafen, Germany), 0.69 MJ NE_L/d

12 ⁵Essential fatty acids and conjugated linoleic acid (EFA+CLA, n = 10): 78 g/d linseed (DERBY[®] Leinöl #4026921003087, DERBY Spezialfutter
13 GmbH, Münster, Germany), 4 g/d safflower oil (GEFRO Distelöl, GEFRO Reformversand Frommlet KG, Memmingen, Germany) and 38 g/d
14 Lutalin[®] (BASF SE, Ludwigshafen, Germany), comprised 0.06 g/d Vitamin E, 2.26 MJ NE_L/d

15 **Supplemental Table S3.** Ingredients and chemical composition of the diets (Vogel et al.,
 16 2020)

Item (g/kg of DM)	Diet	
	Dry period ¹	Lactation
Ingredients		
Corn silage	421	457
Straw	223	97
Compound feed DEFA ² (granulated)	–	446
Dried sugar beet pulp	163	–
Extracted soybean meal	99	–
Rye grain	75	–
Minerals and vitamins ³	10	–
Urea ⁴	9	–
Chemical composition		
NE _L (MJ/kg DM) ⁵	6.5	7.1
Crude fat	21	23
Crude fiber	219	173
Crude protein	141	146
Utilizable protein ⁵	141	143
NFC	379	432
NDF	423	346
ADF	249	197
RNB ⁵⁶	0.0	0.5

17 ¹The dry period diet was fed from wk 6 to 1 before calving. The actual dry period started 40 ±
18 6 d days before birth.

19 ²Ceravis AG, Malchin, Germany

20 Ingredients: 46.5% dried sugar beet pulp, 25.3+ extracted soybean meal, 23.8% grain of rye,
21 1.4% urea, 1.1% premix cow, 1.00% calcium, 0.37% phosphorus, 0.42% sodium, vitamins A,
22 D3, E, copper, ferric, zinc, manganese, cobalt, iodine, selenium

23 Chemical composition: 44.4% NFC, 24.1% crude protein, 21.6% NDF, 12.4% ADF, 9.3%
24 crude fiber, 8.2% crude ash, 1.8% crude fat, 7.9 MJ NE_L/kg DM

25 ³Concentrations of minerals and vitamins (KULMIN[®]MFV Plus, Bergophor

26 Futtermittelfabrik Dr. Berger GmbH & Co., KG, Kulmbach, Germany): 8.5% magnesium,
27 7.5% phosphorus, 6.5% sodium, 3.5% HCl-insoluble ash, 1.5% calcium; vitamins and trace
28 minerals per kg: 1,000,000 I.E. vitamin A, 200,000 I.E. vitamin D₃, 10,000 mg vitamin E, 180
29 mg vitamin B₁, 90 mg vitamin B₂, 90 mg vitamin B₆, 200 mg vitamin B₅, 2500 mg vitamin
30 B₃, 675 mg vitamin B₁₂, 12 mg vitamin B₉, 100 mg vitamin H, 2500 mg zinc, 3500 mg
31 manganese, 500 mg copper, 20mg cobalt, 75 mg iodine, 30 mg selenium as sodium selenite,
32 15 mg Se from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

33 ⁴Piarumin[®] (SKW Stickstoffwerke Piesteritz GmbH, Lutherstadt Wittenberg, Germany):

34 99% urea, 46.5% total nitrogen

35 ⁵German Society of Nutrition Physiology (2001, 2008, 2009) and Deutsche

36 Landwirtschaftliche Gesellschaft (DLG, 2013)

37 ⁶RNB = ruminal nitrogen balance

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41 **Supplemental Table S4.** Fatty acid composition of the experimental diets (Vogel et al., 2020)

Fatty acid (g/kg of DM)	Diet	
	Dry period ¹	Lactation
10:0	0.01	0.01
12:0	0.03	0.04
14:0	0.18	0.12
15:0	0.04	0.04
16:0	4.53	4.73
16:1, <i>cis</i> -9	0.05	0.06
17:0	0.08	0.09
17:1, <i>cis</i> -9	0.01	0.01
18:0	0.60	0.63
18:1, <i>cis</i> -9	3.84	4.82
18:1, <i>cis</i> -11	0.21	0.28
18:2, <i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12	9.32	9.63
18:3, <i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15	1.37	1.35
18:4, <i>cis</i> -6, <i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15	0.02	0.04
20:0	0.16	0.15
20:1, <i>cis</i> -11	0.06	0.08
20:2, <i>cis</i> -11, <i>cis</i> -14	0.02	0.05
21:0	0.02	0.01
22:0	0.25	0.18
22:1, <i>cis</i> -13	—	0.01

22:2, <i>cis</i> -13, <i>cis</i> -16	0.04	0.01
23:0	0.02	0.05
24:0	0.29	0.23
SFA ²	6.21	6.27
MUFA ³	4.17	5.27
PUFA ⁴	10.77	11.08
Sum of n-3 fatty acids ⁵	1.39	1.39
Sum of n-6 fatty acids ⁶	9.38	9.69
Ratio n-6 to n-3	6.76	7.00

42 ¹The Dry period diet was fed from wk 6 to 0 before calving.

43 ²Sum of 10:0; 12:0; 14:0; 15:0; 16:0; 17:0; 18:0; 20:0; 21:0; 22:0; 23:0 and 24:0

44 ³Sum of 16:1 *cis*-9; 17:1 *cis*-9; 18:1 *cis*-9; 18:1 *cis*-11; 20:1 *cis*-11 and 22:1 *cis*-13

45 ⁴Sum of 18:2 *cis*-9, *cis*-12; 18:3 *cis*-9, *cis*-12, *cis*-15; 18:4 *cis*-6, *cis*-9, *cis*-12, *cis*-15; 20:2 *cis*-
46 11, *cis*-14 and 22:2 *cis*-13, *cis*-16

47 ⁵Sum of 18:3 *cis*-9, *cis*-12, *cis*-15 and 18:4 *cis*-6, *cis*-9, *cis*-12, *cis*-15

48 ⁶Sum of 18:2 *cis*-9, *cis*-12; 20:2, *cis*-11, *cis*-14 and 22:2 *cis*-13, *cis*-16

Supplemental Table S5. Characteristics of primers and real-time PCR conditions

Primer ¹	Sequence (5'-3')	Accession number ²	Amplicon size bp	Mean C _q ¹	Annealing °C	Efficiency
Reference genes						
<i>bPPIA</i>		XM_001252497	120	18.19	60	1.86
Forward	GGATTTATGTGCCAGGGTGGTGA					
Reverse	CAAGATGCCAGGACCTGTATG					
<i>bEMD</i>		NM_203361	100	22.76	60	1.86
Forward	GCCCTCAGCTTCACTCTCAGA					
Reverse	GAGGCGTTCCCGATCCTT					
<i>EIK3K</i>		NM_001034489	125	22.19	60	1.85
Forward	CCAGGCCACCAAGAAGAA					
Reverse	TTATACCTTCCAGGAGGTCCATGT					
Genes related to milk fat synthesis						
<i>SREBF1</i>		XM_024980343.1	149	21.63	59	1.88
Forward	GCA CCG AGG CCA AGT TGA AT					
Reverse	CAC CAG GTC CTT CAG CGA TT					
<i>ACACA</i>		NM_174224.2	95	21.69	59	1.87

Forward	TCCTGCTGCTATTGCTACTCCA					
Reverse	CAGTCCCCGCACTCACATAA					
<i>FASN</i>		NM_001012669.1	226	18.31	61	1.83
Forward	ACAGCCTCTTCCTGTTTGACG					
Reverse	CTCTGCACGATCAGCTCGAC					
<i>FABP4</i>		NM_174314.2	101	18.20	60	1.85
Forward	TGGTGCTGGAATGTGTCATGA					
Reverse	TGGAGTTCGATGCAAACGTC					
<i>FADS2</i>		NM_001083444.1	564	29.92	60	1.80
Forward	TTCCGCTGGGAGGAGATTCA					
Reverse	GGCACCCCTTTAAGTGACCGA					
<i>SCD1</i>		XM_027529175	181	18.31	60	1.84
Forward	CCCTTTCCTTGAGCTGTCTG					
Reverse	ATGCTGACTCTCTCCCCTGA					
<i>ELOVL2</i>		NM_001083517.1	180	29.17	62	1.82
Forward	CTCGAGTCAGAGGGTGGTTC					
Reverse	CCAGCATGTATGCGGAGAGA					
<i>ELOVL5</i>		NM_01046597.1	127	25.63	60	1.85
Forward	CCCTCTCGGTTGGTTGTATTC					

Reverse	GTGGTCCTTTTGGTGCTCTCTC					
<i>LPL</i>		BC118091	101	20.49	61	1.86
Forward	ACACAGCTGAGGACACTTGCC					
Reverse	GCCATGGATCACCACAAAGG					
<i>PLIN2</i>		NM_173980.2	211	19.54	62	1.86
Forward	ACAACACACCCCTCAACTGG					
Reverse	CTGCCTGCCTACTTCAGACC					
<i>LPIN1</i>		NM_00126156.2	320	22.71	62	1.84
Forward	CAAAGCTGCCCCATGGAAAC					
Reverse	TTCACACGCCTGGCTTTCA					
Genes related to milk protein synthesis						
<i>SLC7A5</i>		BC126651	107	21.88	61	1.86
Forward	GGGTGACGTAGCCAATCTGG					
Reverse	ATCCCCCATAGGCAAAGAGG					
<i>SLC7A8</i>		EU118967	167	23.42	58	1.87
Forward	GGCCACCCGGGTTCAAGACG					
Reverse	AAGCCAGTGCGATGAGGCCG					
<i>CSN1S1</i>		NM_181029.2	341	11.61	58	1.78
Forward	TTGCTCTTGCCAGGCCTAAA					

Reverse	TTCCAGCTGGGGTACTTTGT					
<i>CSNIS2</i>		NM_174528.2	101	14.12	58	1.80
Forward	CCATTGCCTGGACTACTTGTCT					
Reverse	TTCTTTGCAAGGGCAACAGC					
<i>CSN2</i>		NM_181008	169	11.86	59	1,82
Forward	CAGAAAGCAGTGCCCTATCC					
Reverse	GCCATATTTCCAAGTCGCAGT					
<i>CSN3</i>		BC102120	106	12.86	61	1.86
Forward	GGCGAGCCTACAAGTACACCTA					
Reverse	GGACTGTGTTGATCTCAGGTGG					
<i>EEF1A1</i>		BC105315	101	16.51	60	1.86
Forward	CATCCCAGGCTGACTGTGC					
Reverse	TGTAAGCCAAAAGGGCATGC					
<i>mTOR</i>		DR113626	101	23.98	60	1.87
Forward	CGTTCCTCTCAACATGGACACA					
Reverse	AGCTTCTCCGCGTCTTTACAA					
<i>EIF4EBP1</i>		BC120290	101	22.27	59	1.88
Forward	TTTGAGATGGACATTTAAAGGGC					
Reverse	CTTGCATAAGGCCTGGCTG					
<i>PPARG</i>		Y12420	121	23.45	60	1.88
Forward	AGGATGGGGTCCTCATATCC					

Reverse	GCGTTGAACTTCACAGCAAA					
<i>S6K1</i>		NM_205816.1	97	22.74	60	1.86
Forward	CGGAACAGTCACACACACCT					
Reverse	ACTCCACCAATCCACAGCAC					
Gene related to lactose synthesis						
<i>LALBA</i>		NM_174378.2	273	13.99	58	1.80
Forward	GGAGGTGTCAGTTTGCCTGA					
Reverse	TGCTTTATGGGCCAACCAGT					

¹*PPIA*, peptidylprolyl isomerase A; *bEMD*, emerlin; *EIK3K*, translation initiation factor 3 subunit K, *SREBF1*, sterol regulatory element binding transcription factor 1; *ACACA*, acetyl-CoA carboxylase alpha; *FASN*, fatty acid synthase; *FABP4*, fatty acid binding protein 4; *FADS2*, fatty acid desaturase 2; *SCD1*, stearoyl-CoA-desaturase 1 (delta-9-desaturase); *ELOVL2*, elongase of very long chain fatty acid protein 2; *ELOVL5*, elongase of very long chain fatty acid protein 5; *LPL*, lipoprotein lipase; *PLIN2*, perilipin 2; *LPIN1*, lipin1; *SLC7A5*, solute carrier family 7 member 5; *SLC7A8*, solute carrier family 7 member 8; *CSN1S1*, alpha s1 casein; *CSN1S2*, alpha s2 casein; *CSN2*, beta-casein; *CSN3*, kappa-casein; *EEF1A1*, eukaryotic translation elongation factor 1alpha 1; *mTOR*, mechanistic target of rapamycin; *EIF4EBP1*, BP1 eukaryotic translation initiation factor 4E-binding protein 1; *PPARG*, peroxisome proliferator-activator receptor gamma; *S6K1*, ribosomal protein S6 kinase; *LALBA*, lactalbumin alpha.

²Quantification cycle

³Database used: National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) Entrez Nucleotide (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide>)

Supplemental Figure S1. Protein expression (western blot) of fatty acid synthase (FAS; 273 kDa) in the mammary gland of cows. A) Test for linearity using 25, 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50 μg tissue protein. B) Regression analysis of the linearity blot. C) Protein expression in cows abomasally infused daily with coconut oil (CTRL), linseed and safflower oil (EFA), conjugated linoleic acid (CLA) or the combination of EFA and CLA (EFA+CLA in wk 9 postpartum).

Supplemental Figure S2. Protein expression (western blot) of fatty acid binding protein 4 (FABP4; 15 kDa) in the mammary gland of cows. A) Test for linearity using 25, 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50 μg tissue protein. B) Regression analysis of the linearity blot. C) Protein expression in cows abomasally infused daily with coconut oil (CTRL), linseed and safflower oil (EFA), conjugated linoleic acid (CLA) or the combination of EFA and CLA (EFA+CLA in wk 9 postpartum).

Supplemental Figure S3. Protein expression (western blot) of sterol regulatory element-binding protein 1 (SREBP; 68 kDa) in the mammary gland of cows abomasally infused daily with coconut oil (CTRL), linseed and safflower oil (EFA), conjugated linoleic acid (CLA) or the combination of EFA and CLA (EFA+CLA in wk 9 postpartum).

Supplemental Figure S4. Milk yield immediately before and 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 24, 36, 48, 60, and 72 h after i. v. infusion of [$^{13}\text{C}_6$]-glucose infusion for 4 h in cows abomasally infused daily with coconut oil (○ CTRL; n = 9), linseed and safflower oil (▲ EFA; n = 9), CLA (▼ n = 10), or the combination of EFA and CLA (◆ EFA+CLA; n = 10) during late gestation and early lactation. Data are presented as LSM \pm SE.

Supplemental Figure S5. Enrichment of ^{13}C -glucose (mol % excess; MPE) in blood plasma at 60, 120, 150, 180, 210, and 240 min after [$^{13}\text{C}_6$]-glucose administration in cows abomasally infused daily with coconut oil (○ CTRL; n = 9), linseed and safflower oil (▲ EFA; n = 9), CLA (▼ n = 10), or the combination of EFA and CLA (◆ EFA+CLA; n = 10) on d 21 postpartum. Data are presented as LSM \pm SE. Sample collection was described by Vogel et al. (2021). The values from 150 min to 240 min after the start of the tracer infusion show the plateau of ^{13}C -glucose enrichment. The area under the curve (AUC; LSM \pm SE were 58.5 ± 2.5 , 57.1 ± 2.2 , 59.9 ± 2.3 , and 60.3 ± 2.1 MPE \times min for groups CTRL, EFA, CLA, and EFA+CLA, respectively) calculated from this showed no group effects: P = 0.9 for EFA treatment, P = 0.3 for CLA treatment, and P = 0.7 for EFA \times CLA interaction. The statistical model is described in the paper.

Supplemental Figure S6. Relationship between ^{13}C enrichment in milk fat (TG; triglycerides) and in glycerol of the TG in milk. For the comparative measurement, 20 cows (Hötger, K., H. M. Hammon, C. Weber, S. Görs, A. Tröscher, R. M. Bruckmaier, and C. C. Metges. 2013. Supplementation of conjugated linoleic acid in dairy cows reduces endogenous glucose production during early lactation. *J. Dairy Sci.* 96:2258-2270. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3168/jds.2012-6127>.) were used and measurements were taken at 6, 16, and 26 hours after the start of the i. v. [$^{13}\text{C}_6$]-glucose infusion.

